

Law, AI and robotics: Germany

[WP4 – AI and robotics]

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Due date	29 March 2019
Delivery date	7 December 2018
Type	Report
Dissemination level	PU = Public
Keywords	Legal analysis, artificial intelligence, AI law, AI regulation, robotics, robotics regulation, Germany country report

The SIENNA project - *Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact* - has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716.

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Abstract

This report provides an overview of the legal framework and legal developments regarding Artificial Intelligence and robotics (AI&R) in Germany. The most challenging issues from a legal perspective are right now safety and liability, privacy and ownership issues which might occur during the use of robots or AI systems. These issues, and the question if new regulations or a revision of existing laws and guidelines is necessary are discussed in the German mainstream press and in some academic articles (however, the focus is more on the robot rules currently discussed on EU level, than on regulations for Germany).

There were two important actions from the government regarding AI&R legislation in the last few years: The German Road Traffic Act was changed to create a legal framework for the use of self-driving vehicles. Furthermore, special rules for the use of drones have been implemented to regulate privacy and safety issues.

In 2018, the German government established a permanent working group on AI at the German Bundestag and a Data Ethics Committee. Together they have developed a strategy on AI for Germany, which was published in November 2018 and includes an action point on “revising the legal framework”.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V1	24 Oct 2018	First Draft		TRI, National legal expert
V2	7 Dec 2018	Final Version	Review by TRI and national legal expert + feedback from Warsaw workshop	7 Dec 2018

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
Task 4.2	This report is part of and, will provide input to deliverable 4.2.

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Executive summary

This report presents the outcomes of our research on legal developments and trends in the law on Artificial Intelligence and robotics (AI&R) in Germany. There were two important AI&R-relevant legislative actions in the last few years: The German Road traffic Act was changed to create rules for the use of self-driving vehicles. Furthermore, special rules for the use of drones have been implemented to regulate privacy and safety issues.

The German federal government published a strategy on AI in November 2018.¹ Revising the regulatory framework and ensuring legal certainty is one of the action points outlined. National and international networking is very important for Germany. Joint guidelines with other leading regions and economic areas is a central policy goal. Germany will develop new regulations together with the new German data ethics committee, established in September 2018, and with the EU high-level expert group on AI. Another goal is the protection of basic values and principles, such as freedom of action, self-determination and protection of privacy. Therefore, the government wants to observe carefully if the new data protection law can protect people's privacy while AI&R technologies are getting more powerful. Furthermore, safety and liability issues, questions regarding transparency of AI-algorithms, and ownership issues are in focus of Germany's AI strategy.

These issues and the question whether new regulations or a revision of existing law and guidelines is necessary has been discussed in the German mainstream press and in some academic articles. However, the focus here is more on the robot rules currently discussed on EU level, than on regulations for Germany.

¹ German Federal Government, *Strategie Künstliche Intelligenz der Bundesregierung (Strategy for AI) 2018*.
<https://www.ki-strategie-deutschland.de/home.html>

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial intelligence
AI&R	Artificial intelligence and robotics
CE	Conformité Européene
D	Deliverable
EEA	European Economic Area
EPC	Convention on the Grant of European Patents
GDPR	General data protection regulation
PatG	Patent Act
TAB	Office of Technology Assessment at the German Bundestag (Büro für Technikfolgen-Abschätzung beim Deutschen Bundestag)
WP	Work package

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Artificial intelligence	The science and engineering of machines with capabilities that are considered intelligent (i.e., intelligent by the standard of <i>human</i> intelligence). Major applications of AI technology are in transportation, education, finance, industry, healthcare, marketing, management, telecommunications, entertainment and defence, amongst other fields. Important subfields of AI were found to include: knowledge representation and automated reasoning, artificial neural networks, machine learning, computer vision, computer audition, natural language processing, expert systems, data mining, intelligent agent systems and automated planning, evolutionary computation. [SIENNA D4.1]
Robotics	The field of science and engineering that deals with the design, construction, operation, and application of robots. Major applications of robots are in transportation, industry, healthcare, education, entertainment, space exploration, defence, retail, companionship, housekeeping and other areas. Important subfields of robotics were found to include: robot mechanics, robot sensing, robot control (including many subareas, such as robot learning, adaptive control, developmental robotics, evolutionary robotics, cognitive robotics, behaviour-based robotics, robotic mapping and planning), robot locomotion, bio-inspired and soft robotics, humanoid robotics, microrobotics, nanorobotics, beam robotics, cloud robotics, swarm robotics, telerobotics, social robotics and human-robot interaction. [SIENNA D4.1]
Automated decision-	Decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which

Term	Explanation
making	produces legal effects concerning a data subject or similarly significantly affects him or her (GDPR, Article 22 (1)). It refers to individual decision-making made by automated means without any human involvement. Examples include: an online decision to award a loan; and a recruitment aptitude test which uses pre-programmed algorithms and criteria. ² (Information Commissioner's Office)
Machine learning	A set of approaches within AI where statistical techniques and data are used to “teach” computer systems how to perform particular tasks, without these systems being explicitly programmed to do so. (SIENNA D4.1, p. 11.)

Table 2: Glossary of terms

² <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/individual-rights/rights-related-to-automated-decision-making-including-profiling/>

1. Introduction

Germany has a civil law system founded on the principles laid out by the Basic Law³ for the Federal Republic of Germany. It is made up of the national, federal government (the Bund) and the 16 regional states (the Länder). The powers and functions of the federal government and the regional states are strongly separated.⁴ Both have their own executive, legislative and judiciary branches. Federal legislative power is divided between the *German Bundestag*, which is directly elected by the German citizens and the *Bundesrat* which presents the governments of the 16 regional states. The Bundestag has more influence than the *Bundesrat*. Although, the agreement of the *Bundesrat* in the legislative process is often required, since federal legislation frequently has to be executed by state or local agencies. The *German Bundestag* is the most important body pertaining to the adoption of a new law or changing existing law. The deputies and parliamentary groups of the Bundestag can introduce new or revised laws into the Bundestag as drafts. Here the debate, consultation and vote on the bill take place after a fixed procedure. Since the federal states have a substantial share of state power in the federal state system, the Federal Council is also involved in the legislative process. It gets all the laws to vote and can even fail a draft depending on the nature of the law.

The **objective** of this report is to give an overview of the current law and legal developments in AI and robotics (AI&R) in Germany. Furthermore, this report provides information about the regulatory bodies that are involved in the legal debate on AI&R in Germany.

The primary method used was desktop research using keywords such as : “Künstliche Intelligenz” (“Artificial Intelligence”), “Robotik” (“robotic”), “big data”, “selbstfahrende Autos” (“self driving cars”), “machine learning” + “Gesetz” (“law”), “Regeln” (“guidelines”), “Bundestag” (“federal government”), “Gesetzesentwurf” (“draft law”). Various sources were consulted, e.g., Juris⁵, BELIT⁶ and Google.

Recent policy documents

There are three significant reports that have focused to varying degrees on legal issues related to AI&R in Germany:

- Key points for AI developed by the federal government in 2018.⁷ The final strategy on AI will be published at the digital summit in Nuremberg⁸ in December 2018. One key point focuses on the necessity of a new legal framework to cover AI&R issues.
- Paper on “Robotics in the care sector” published by the German Bundestag in 2017.⁹

³ Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany.

⁴ For further information on the German legal system see the report developed by the SATORI project. SATORI, “Ethics assessments in different countries. Germany”, 2015. <http://satoriproject.eu/media/4.e-Country-report-Germany.pdf>

⁵ Juris is the most common German legal database. <https://www.juris.de/jportal/index.jsp>

⁶ <http://www.drze.de/belit/recherche/schnellsuche/recherche.html>

⁷ German federal government, *Keypoints for Artificial Intelligence*, 2018.

https://www.bmwi.de/Redaktion/EN/Downloads/E/key-points-for-federal-government-strategy-on-artificial-intelligence.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4

⁸ <https://www.de.digital/DIGITAL/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

- Law on self- driving cars.¹⁰ For more information see Section 3 of this report.

Legal academic discourses dealing with legal issues and regulation of AI&R

To identify the relevant national legal academic literature three databases were used:

- BELIT (<http://www.drze.de/belit/>)
- Google scholar (<https://scholar.google.co.uk>)
- Juris ([www.juris .de](http://www.juris.de))

The following search terms were used (in German and in English language) in the desktop search:

Search terms	
ENGLISH	GERMAN TRANSLATION
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Künstliche Intelligenz (KI)
Robotics/robot	Robotik/Roboter
Deep learning	Deep learning
Algorithm	Algorithmen
Big data	Big data, große Datenmengen
Machine learning	Maschinelles Lernen
Prosthetics	Assisitive/prothetische Technologien
Human-Machine-Interfaces	Mensch-Maschine Verschmelzung
Regulation/law for robots	Robotergesetze

The relevant legal debate in Germany focuses mainly on big data, autonomous driving cars, robots in health care and impacts of AI developments on privacy, responsibility and safety. The following relevant articles were found:

- Beck S., “Grundlegende Fragen zum rechtlichen Umgang mit der Robotik“ (english translation: Basic questions about the legal handling of robotics), *Juristische Rundschau*, pp. 225-230, 2009.
- Denga, M., “Deliktische Haftung für künstliche Intelligenz“ (english translation: Delictional liability for artificial intelligence), *Computer und Recht* 2018, pp. 69-78.
- Günther J., M. Böglmüller, “Künstliche Intelligenz und Roboter in der Arbeitswelt“ (english translation: Artificial intelligence and robots in the workplace), *Betriebs-Berater* 2017, pp. 53-58.
- Hamsch, J., D. Gorr, “In den sicheren Armen des Roboters“ (english translation: In the safe arms of the robot), *Versicherungs Wirtschaft* 3, 2017, pp. 66-67.
- Hennes D., Schwalbe, U., “Kartellbildung durch lernende Algorithmen?“ (english translation: Cartel formation through learning algorithms?), *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung*, 2018.
- Mitterer, K., Wiedemann, M., Zwissler, T., “BB-Gesetzgebungs- und Rechtsprechungsreport zu Industrie 4.0 und Digitalisierung 2017“ (english translation: BB Legislative and Judicial Report on Industry 4.0 and Digitization 2017), in: *Betriebs-Berater* 2018, pp. 3-15.

⁹ German Bundestag, Office of Technology assessment at the German Bundestag, “Robotics in the care sector - challenges for society,” 2017. <http://www.tab-beim-bundestag.de/en/pdf/publications/tab-fokus/TAB-Fokus-017.pdf>

¹⁰ Deutscher Bundestag, Gesetzentwurf der Bundesregierung, Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Änderung des Straßenverkehrsgesetzes, 2017. (Draft for a change of the road traffic act) <http://dip21.bundestag.de/dip21/btd/18/113/1811300.pdf>

- Schuhr J., Willensfreiheit, Roboter und Auswahlaxiom (Freedom of choice, robots and axiom of choice), in: Beck S. (eds.), *Jenseits von Mensch und Maschine: ethische und rechtliche Fragen zum Umgang mit Robotern, Künstlicher Intelligenz und Cyborgs*, 2012, pp. 43-75.
- Simmler M., Markwalder N., “Roboter in der Verantwortung?” (english translation: robots and responsibility), in: *Zeitschrift für die gesamte Strafrechtswissenschaft* 2017, p. 20.
- Spindler G., “Roboter, Automation, künstliche Intelligenz, selbst-steuernde Kfz – Braucht das Recht neue Haftungskategorien?” (english translation: Robots, automation, artificial intelligence, self-driving vehicles - Does the law need new liability categories?), *Computer und Recht*, 31(12), 2015, pp. 766-776.
- Teubner G., *Digital Personhood? The Status of Autonomous Software Agents in Private Law*, 2018. <https://www.jura.uni-frankfurt.de/71719886/Digital-PersonhoodENGancilla2018.pdf>
- The German Federal Association of Corporate Lawyers (BUJ) and commercial law firm CMS: study on “Digital Economy and the Law”.
<http://www.digitalisierungsstudie.com/index.php/de/startseite-digitalisierungsstudie-buj-cms-hasche-sigle>

2. Scope and limitations of the report

This report has a limited scope as demarcated by the SIENNA task 4.2 workplan. It does not comprehensively cover all aspects of AI&R (given that both these are vast topics in themselves, spanning a range of applications and sectors) regulation and all legal issues arising from such technologies but has taken up for study a limited range of topics with high policy and human rights significance.

As of December 2018, there is a debate about new legal frameworks for Germany covering AI&R-related issues. However, at the moment, it is difficult to specify concrete legal developments, since not much has happened yet. This is expected to be addressed by the German government in the near future.

3. Legal developments

This section examines German legal developments pertaining to AI&R covering the last five to ten years. We searched on Google, on government websites, on websites from institutions which work for the government, on Juris and on websites of professional organisations.

Are there new regulatory bodies being set up to regulate AI&R? What are the developments on this front? (e.g., AI watchdogs, AI commission, Robotics commission)

- The Study Commission at the German Bundestag "Artificial Intelligence – Social Responsibility and Economic Potential"¹¹ was established as a new regulatory body in June 2018.
 - The study commission has 19 members.

¹¹ https://www.bundestag.de/en/committees/bodies/study/artificial_intelligence

- “The Study Commission, comprises in equal parts of Members of the German Bundestag and external experts in the relevant field, aims to investigate the future influence of artificial intelligence (AI) on our lives, our way of living together, the German economy and the future world of work. The opportunities presented by AI for society, politics and the economy are examined alongside the challenges. A host of technical, legal and ethical issues are the subject of discussion. The Commission’s role also includes identifying and outlining the need for policy-based action at national, European and international level on the basis of their investigative results, in order to capitalise on the economic and social opportunities offered by AI on the one hand, while also minimising the risks on the other.”¹²
- The German “Data Ethics Commission” was established in September 2018:
 - It was created by the Federal Government. The Commission works independently, with support from the Federal Ministry of Justice and Consumer Protection and the Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community.
 - The Data Ethics Commission is composed of 16 experts from the fields of medicine, law, computer science, statistics, economics, theology, ethics and journalism.
 - Important documents published by the Data Ethics Commission are:
 - Recommendations of the Data Ethics Commission for the Federal Government’s Strategy on Artificial Intelligence.¹³
 - The Federal Government’s key questions to the Data Ethics Commission.¹⁴
- The Office of Technology Assessment at the German Bundestag (Büro für Technikfolgen-Abschätzung beim Deutschen Bundestag (TAB)¹⁵ was established in 1990.
 - The TAB is an independent scientific institution that advises the German Bundestag and its committees on matters relating to research and technology.
 - The objectives of technology assessment, as TAB sees it, are the following:
 - To analyse the potentials of new scientific and technological developments and explore the associated opportunities,
 - To examine the societal, regulatory and economic framework conditions for implementation and application of scientific and technological developments,
 - To analyse potential impacts of technologies in a comprehensive and forward-looking manner, pinpoint the opportunities offered by using a technology and indicate possible means of avoiding or reducing its risks,
 - All this is the basis for developing options for action by political decision-makers.
- The federal ministry of education and sciences has founded three new big data centers in Germany, within the framework of the funding program “competence centers for the intelligent use of Big Data”:
 - Berlin Big Data Center (lead TU Berlin)¹⁶

¹² https://www.bundestag.de/en/committees/bodies/study/artificial_intelligence

¹³ https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/EN/themen/it-digital-policy/recommendations-data-ethics-commission.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3

¹⁴ https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/EN/themen/it-digital-policy/key-questions-Data-Ethics-commission.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4

¹⁵ <http://www.tab-beim-bundestag.de/en/index.html>

- Competence Center for Scalable Data Services and Solutions (Lead TU Dresden and University of Leipzig)¹⁷
- Smart Data Innovation Lab (Lead Karlsruhe Institute for Technologies)¹⁸.

Have developments in AI (i.e., automated decision-making systems, algorithmic systems, machine learning) and robotics led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights?

Developments in AI&R are currently part of the political and legal debate in Germany, although this remains at the discussion level. Human rights legislation has not been changed in response to AI&R developments.

One relevant legal development that has some influence is the revision of data protection law through the application of the *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR)¹⁹ in May 2018 and accordingly the revision of the German Data Protection law (“Bundesdatenschutzverordnung – BDSG”)²⁰ Relevant for AI&R developments is especially section 31 BDSG, on the protection of commercial transactions in the case of scoring and credit reports.

Section 31 (1) BDSG:

For the purpose of deciding on the creation, execution or termination of a contractual relationship with a natural person, the use of a probability value for certain future action by this person (scoring) shall be permitted only if

1. the provisions of data protection law have been followed;
2. the data used to calculate the probability value are demonstrably essential for calculating the probability of the action on the basis of a scientifically recognized mathematic-statistical procedure;
3. other data in addition to address data are used to calculate the probability value; and
4. if address data are used, the data subject was notified ahead of time of the planned use of these data; this notification shall be documented.

Have there been/are there attempts or plans to create or adopt new legislation in response to developments in AI&R (e.g., granting legal personhood to robots, prescribing civil or criminal liability for harms caused), or to regulate²¹ how AI&R applications are designed, set up, commissioned or used? (e.g., regulation of algorithmic development or restrictions on the use of robots in certain conditions or sectors)

There have been some developments on this front, notably in relation to drones, and autonomous driving cars.

¹⁶ <http://big-data-berlin.dima.tu-berlin.de/home/>

¹⁷ <https://www.scads.de/en/>

¹⁸ <https://www.sdil.de/en/>

¹⁹ General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

²⁰ Bundesdatenschutzgesetz vom 30. Juni 2017 (BGBl. I S. 2097). English translation: https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_bdsch_g/

²¹ This could be to restrict or advance the development or use of such applications.

Drones: In 2017, the German Ministry of Transport published regulations for the use of drones.²² Even though significant regulatory restrictions apply, flying drones for private or commercial purposes is allowed. Weight-related regulatory obligations have been set: The use of drones with a weight below 0.25 kilograms (kg) is generally unregulated. All drones above this weight require a fireproof identification tag from 1 October 2017. Pilots flying a drone with a weight of more than 2 kg must take a theoretical examination. Drones with a weight of more than 5 kg require an additional license. While the use of drones with a weight above 25 kg is generally prohibited, operators can apply for derogations. Furthermore, drone operators must respect the privacy of other people insofar as it is not allowed to fly above or closer than 100 metres to gatherings of people and scenes of accidents, government buildings, nature reserves and housing areas without the (beneficial) owner(s) having given their consent.

Autonomous driving cars: In June 2017, rules for autonomous driving cars came into force as the 8th amendment of the German road traffic regulation.²³ Automobile manufacturers are allowed to test autonomous driving cars, if they follow the prescribed rules. These include:

- a human must be in the driver's seat at all times;
- human life should always have priority over property or animal life;
- a surveillance system must record activity in order to determine the cause of any accident (like a black box in aircraft).

In addition, drivers should be able to decide what personal information is collected from a vehicle. Drivers would thus be able to prevent such data from being used to customise advertising.

Due to the technical developments that are progressing rapidly in this area, these rules will be reviewed again in 2019 and, if necessary, improved. Most manufacturers do not expect autonomous cars before 2020 to be able to handle all traffic situations independently. Currently there is a debate about who is legally liable in case of an accident involving such vehicles. According to the rules defined in the road traffic regulation, the driver will bear responsibility for accidents that take place under his or her watch, although if the self-driving system is in charge and a system failure is to blame, the manufacturer will be responsible. This rule is criticised in the legal scholarship debate as the liability regulations leave much room for interpretation and do not really adequately address the liability issue.²⁴

Identify any significant case law or judgments²⁵ addressing human rights challenges of AI&R (if there are no judgments, you can refer to legal doctrine)

Based on desktop research,²⁶ we only identified one relevant judgement on an operation with a robot.²⁷ During an operation, in which a hip was replaced with an artificial hip, a physician used a

²² Verordnung zur Regelung des Betriebs von unbemannten Fluggeräten. 30. März 2017, in: Bundesgesetzblatt Jahrgang 2017 Teil I Nr. 17, ausgegeben zu Bonn am 6. April 2017, pp. 683-688.

<https://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/DE/Anlage/LF/verordnung-zur-regelung-des-betriebs-von-unbemannten-fluggeraeten.pdf?blob=publicationFile>

²³ Straßenverkehrsgesetz in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 5. März 2003 (BGBl. I S. 310, 919), das zuletzt durch Artikel 6 des Gesetzes vom 17. August 2017 (BGBl. I S. 3202) geändert worden ist

²⁴ Cf. Wolfers B., Selbstfahrende Autos: Ist das erlaubt?, in: Recht, Automobil, Wirtschaft, 2017.

https://www.freshfields.com/globalassets/our-thinking/campaigns/digital/iot/cars/pdf/beitrag_wolfers_raw_01_17.pdf

²⁵ Limited only to decisions in the highest courts.

²⁶ We searched in the following databases:

robot. Unfortunately, a nerve was damaged and after the operation the patient suffered permanent pain. The patient sued the physician who performed the operation for damages and compensation. The court rejected the complaint with the explanation that the patient was properly informed and the nerve damage was one of the risks that could occur.

Highlight any other relevant, potential future legal developments relating to AI&R identified in authoritative legal sources in your country

As highlighted before, the German federal government worked on a strategy on AI and published key points in June 2018.²⁸ Revising the regulatory framework and ensuring legal certainty is one of the action points outlined. The strategy states:

The increasing use of AI may necessitate changes to the regulatory framework in order to give providers investment security and legal certainty and to establish a basis for justified trust and acceptance on the part of users. Here, the following points need to be observed:

- Review and, if necessary, revision of the regulatory framework for the use of data and the application of AI technology, and in particular clarification of the legal relationship between the parties. We will take account of proposals by the Data Ethics Commission.
- Ensuring transparency, traceability and reviewability of AI systems to permit effective protection against distortions, discrimination, manipulation and other abuses, particularly where algorithm-based forecasting and decision-making systems are used.
- Promotion of the development of innovative applications which bolster self-determination, social inclusion and privacy of citizens.
- Strengthening of the social partnership in the integration of AI into the world of work.
- Adaptation of the copyright rules in order to make it easier to use text and data mining (TDM) as a basis for machine learning for both commercial and non-commercial purposes. Here, a fair balance should be struck between the various interests.²⁹

Moreover, national and international networking is another action point and therefore the “(d)ialogue and if possible agreement on joint guidelines with other leading regions and economic areas”³⁰ is a central goal. The strategy outlines:

We are open to international cooperation in the field of AI and will seek bilateral and multilateral cooperation for this, e.g. in the G7 and G20 context. German missions abroad and German Science and Innovation Houses can be used for this type of cooperation. In this process, we will base our approach on the values we apply in terms of use of AI systems.³¹

4. Specific legal issues

This section explores selected specific legal issues related to AI&R. We explore for AI, two critical issues:

www.juris.de; <http://www.rechtsprechung-im-internet.de/jportal/portal/page/bsirsprod.psmi>;
<https://justiz.de/onlinedienste/rechtsprechung/index.php>; <https://dejure.org/>

²⁷ BGH, Urteil vom 13. Juni 2006 - VI ZR 323/04 - OLG Frankfurt a.M.

²⁸ https://www.bmwi.de/Redaktion/EN/Downloads/E/key-points-for-federal-government-strategy-on-artificial-intelligence.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4

²⁹ BMWI 2018, p.7-8.

³⁰ BMWI 2018, p.8.

³¹ BMWI 2018, p.8.

- Algorithmic bias and discrimination (including automated decision-making systems). How does the law deal with issues of algorithmic bias and discrimination?
- Intellectual property issues related to works created by AI. Does the law ascribe intellectual property rights (e.g., copyright, patent right, design rights, trademarks etc) for AI-generated works or inventions? Who owns such intellectual property rights?

For robotics, we explore:

- Creation of a specific legal status for robots, i.e., legal personhood or electronic personality. Has the law created or does the law recognise a specific legal status for robots? Are there any movements in this direction?
- Safety and civil liability issues: who is liable for damage caused by robots?

4.1 Artificial intelligence

4.1.1 Algorithmic bias and discrimination (including automated decision-making systems)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)³² contains (albeit indirectly) safeguards against automated decisions, including those based on profiling (which would have the potential to create discriminatory effects), that have a legal or similarly significant effect on individuals. Article 22 (1) states, “The data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her.”

For Germany, Section 22 of the DSGVO on “Automated individual decision-making, including profiling” is relevant.

1. The data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her.
2. Paragraph 1 shall not apply if the decision:
 - (a) is necessary for entering into, or performance of, a contract between the data subject and a data controller;
 - (b) is authorised by Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject and which also lays down suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests; or
 - (c) is based on the data subject's explicit consent.
3. In the cases referred to in points (a) and (c) of paragraph 2, the data controller shall implement suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.
4. Decisions referred to in paragraph 2 shall not be based on special categories of personal data referred to in Article 9(1), unless point (a) or (g) of Article 9(2) applies and suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests are in place.

³² The new Data Protection Act came into force in Germany on 25 May 2018.

4.1.2 Intellectual property issues related to works created by AI

Applications for German patents are made under the Patent Act (PatG) while European patents are applied for under the Convention on the Grant of European Patents (EPC). The German Patent Act has largely been harmonised with the provisions of the EPC.

Para. 1 no. 1 PatG and § 52 no. 1 EPC agree in stating that patents can be granted in respect of inventions which are new, are based on inventive activity and which are commercially usable. According to section 3 1) PatG, “an invention shall be deemed to be new if it does not form part of the state of the art. The state of the art shall be held to comprise all knowledge made available to the public before the date governing the filing or priority date of the application by means of a written or oral description, by use or in any other way.” Relevant for the patent of AI-generated work are furthermore Sections 4 and 5 of the German PatG:

Section 4: “An invention shall be deemed to involve an inventive step if, having regard to the state of the art, it is not obvious to a person skilled in the art. If the state of the art also includes documents within the meaning of section 3 (2), these documents shall not be considered in deciding whether there has been an inventive step.”

Section 5: “An invention shall be deemed to be susceptible of industrial application if it can be made or used in any kind of industry, including agriculture.”

The German Patent and Trade Mark Office (Deutsches Patent und Marken Amt – DPMA) organised a workshop on “AI and intellectual property rights: How can future technology be protected?” in November 2018. At this event, stakeholders from various sectors of industry such as automotive, energy, materials, medical technology and electronics and IT came together. One speaker questioned, “Are AI-generated inventions patentable?” and suggested that if AI-generated inventions were patentable, there would be a danger that competition would concentrate too much: “Large, rich companies could literally plaster patents on the market. There would no longer be a transfer of knowledge.”³³ Furthermore, he described that patents on AI results could be an important incentive to continue investing in AI and their publication would enhance the state of the art. “However, if a company protects its AI-generated inventions by keeping them secret, the technology state of the art remains the same for all others.”³⁴

At the workshop the participants also discussed the question if self-applying for a patent by an AI should, or rather, could be possible. Currently, this is not possible from a legal point of view, as only natural persons can apply for patents, and an AI is not a natural person.

4.2 Robotics

4.2.1 Creation of a specific legal status for robots

The question whether robots or other autonomous digital systems should have rights and obligations or a legal status is discussed in Germany more in the media than in academic circles. The search in Google and BELIT brought up a lot of relevant press articles and interviews with politics discussing

³³ https://www.dpma.de/english/our_office/publications/background/ai/aiconferenceatdpma/index.html

³⁴ https://www.dpma.de/english/our_office/publications/background/ai/aiconferenceatdpma/index.html

the question if we need a new robot law?³⁵ Relevant articles in popular German newspapers discussed, e.g., “robots need rights and obligations”³⁶, “Rights for robots?”.³⁷ However, these discussions focus merely on international law and on ethical and legal issues in general and not on national law. The developments on EU level regarding laws for robots are discussed often. The question how we could implement such EU regulations in German law is not a topic.

In the legal scholarship debate, the focus is similar.³⁸ Some scholars discuss EU developments and very few give statements on legal gaps in the German law. The leading opinion seems to be that robots should have no legal status, since they are not persons and therefore neither liable nor have any rights.

4.2.2 Safety and civil liability issues: who is liable for damage caused by robots?

Robots and liability issues according to the Product liability Act

In the German scholarship, there is some discussion regarding the legal framework that deals with liability issues in human-robot interaction.³⁹ One of the issues is when a robot and a human are involved in an accident in Germany, who is responsible for the accident? If the manufacturer or seller of a robot (if it can be classed as a ‘product’) and the person who buys the robot have a contract, according to the German Product Liability Act (“Produkthaftungsgesetz”), the seller or rather manufacturer is liable for the proper function of the robot. “In such case as a defective product causes a person’s death, injury to his body or damage to his health, or damage to an item of property, the producer of the product has an obligation to compensate the injured person for the resulting damage.”⁴⁰ However, these provisions are not applicable to a product that is significantly changed by use and based on the user-provided information. As stated, “The producer’s liability obligation is excluded if under the circumstances it is probable that the defect which caused the damage did not exist at the time when the producer put the product into circulation.”⁴¹ The leading opinion in German scholarship debate is that the rules outlined in the Product Liability Act are not sufficient to cover legal issues concerning new robot technologies.⁴²

³⁵ See e.g., <https://www.n-tv.de/wissen/Roboter-Recht-bringt-Juristen-ins-Gruebeln-article20491016.html>; <https://www.lto.de/recht/legal-tech/l/digitalisierung-rechte-fuer-roboter-elektronische-person-rechtspersoenlichkeit/>; <https://www.deutscheranwaltspiegel.de/haben-roboter-rechte/>; <https://www.zeit.de/2016/40/legal-tech-algorithmen-juristen-ersatz>.

³⁶ Charisius H., Roboter brauchen Rechte und Pflichten, *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 2017, <https://www.sueddeutsche.de/wissen/kuenstliche-intelligenz-roboter-brauchen-rechte-und-pflichten-1.3330222>

³⁷ Marsiske H.A., Rechte für Roboter?, *Heise*, 2016. <https://www.heise.de/newsticker/meldung/Rechte-fuer-Roboter-3334639.html>

³⁸ See e.g., Beck 2009; Denga, Simmler/Markwalder 2017.

³⁹ Beck, S.: Brauchen wir ein Roboterrecht? Ausgewählte juristische Fragen zum Zusammenleben von Menschen und Robotern. <https://www.jdzb.de/fileadmin/Redaktion/PDF/veroeffentlichungen/tagungsbaende/D62/11%20p1338%20beck.pdf>

⁴⁰Product Liability Act Section (1).

⁴¹ Product Liability Act Section 1 (2), 4.

⁴² Cf. Hilgendorf E., Automatisiertes Fahren und Strafrecht - der "Aschaffenburg Fall" (selfdriving cars), *DRiZ*, pp. 66-69, 2018

4.3 Other key specific legal issues related to AI&R that are at the forefront and how they are being addressed

In addition to the above issues, key issues at the forefront of the legal discussion in Germany in relation to AI&R are:

AI & robotics in the health sector

In Germany, there is discussion about the necessity of new regulations in reaction to developments of AI&R in the health sector, especially with regard to screening and diagnosis. One central issue is the development of software solutions in the health care system and the legal classification of the product. It has to be determined if the software is a medical product. This is of importance because medical devices may only be placed on the market if they bear a CE⁴³ marking after carrying out a conformity assessment procedure. If a product that qualifies as a medical device is marketed without a CE mark, there is a risk that a competitor will require the distribution to be discontinued. In addition, placing the product on the market constitutes an administrative offence and may even have criminal consequences.

According to the German Medical Devices Act (MPG),⁴⁴ the intended purpose of the software is important. If the software detects or treats illnesses, it is classified as a medical device – for example, if it supports the diagnosis, facilitates decisions about therapeutic measures or calculates the dosage of medicines. On the other hand, if the software only provides knowledge or only stores data, there is no medical device available. Since the manufacturer determines the purpose, there is some leeway through the functional design of the application.

At the civil law level, many questions regarding AI&R developments in the health sector have not been answered conclusively. E.g., the conclusion of contracts, liability for errors and injuries and insurance are not regulated. If a robot is used during a surgery or a treatment, it is not always clear according to German law, who is liable, if the robot makes a mistake.

Restricting robot surveillance

Germany's Federal Network Agency (Bundesnetzagentur), which regulates telecommunications, gas, and banned toys which could collect and send private data, based on section 90 of the German Telecommunications Act. Forbidden toys are, e.g., the doll "My Friend Cayla" and smart watches for children. Both toys have microphones and a transmitter.

5. Brief analysis of gaps and challenges

⁴³ CE marking is a certification mark that indicates conformity with health, safety, and environmental protection standards for products sold within the European Economic Area (EEA).

⁴⁴ The Act on Medical Devices of 2nd August 1994 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 1963), in the version of 7th August 2002 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 3146), last amended by Article 12 of the Act of 24th July 2010 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 983).

At first glance, German law seems to be prepared for some developments in AI&R: The new German data protection law includes a new section on scoring and regulation for profiling; liability issues are regulated in the Product Liability Act and the Patent Act broadly covers patent-related issues. However, a deeper look reveals that there are many legal gaps, which show that existing regulations are not adequate to regulate the issues concerning AI&R developments: It is not clear that the new data protection regulation will be sufficient to protect the persons privacy. For harm or damage caused as consequence of using a robot, it is not clear in all cases, how the Product Liability Act should be interpreted. Furthermore, the Patent Act does not outline how to proceed with patents for AI&R developments. These are the challenges Germany has to address in the next years.

6. Conclusion

There have been legal developments relating to AI&R in Germany, such as the new law on self-driving cars, the new data protection regulation and rules for the use of drones. However, as shown in the public media, press articles and in academic articles, the most relevant issues concerning AI&R are not yet properly regulated - these are privacy issues, ownership issues and safety and civil liability issues.

As outlined above, the German federal government has developed a strategy on AI and published draft key points in July 2018;⁴⁵ subsequently, on 16. November 2018, the final strategy was published.⁴⁶ Revising the regulatory framework and ensuring legal certainty is one of the action points outlined (action field no. 9).⁴⁷ One of the main goals described in the strategy on AI under action field 9, is the protection of basic values and principles, such as the freedom of action, self-determination and protection of privacy.

During the development of the AI strategy, stakeholders, especially from industry and IT experts were consulted in panels and interviews about their views on legal gaps and developments regarding AI. The result was that there is a conflict: Some do not want further regulations, since they are afraid of investment constraints, others argue for new regulations, especially to avoid lack of transparency and copyright issues for text and data-mining. The government has decided to review if new regulations are necessary to ensure transparency and full traceability of AI systems. Furthermore, the government will examine if the new data protection regulation is sufficient to protect self-determination and privacy. Moreover, legal regulations for the use of non-personal data will be proofed and if necessary revised. Suggestions from the German Data ethics commission⁴⁸ will be taken into account, especially those referring to the transparent documentation of the use of data and AI-algorithms. The government wants to ensure that the use of data is only possible under the non-discrimination principle, and in accordance with the right to privacy.

⁴⁵ https://www.bmwi.de/Redaktion/EN/Downloads/E/key-points-for-federal-government-strategy-on-artificial-intelligence.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4

⁴⁶ German federal government, Strategie Künstliche Intelligenz der Bundesregierung (Strategy for AI) 2018. <https://www.ki-strategie-deutschland.de/home.html>

⁴⁷ For further information on the other action fields see here: <https://www.ki-strategie-deutschland.de/home.html>

⁴⁸ <https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/pressemitteilungen/EN/2018/data-ethics-commission.html>

Moreover, the government announced a revision of the copyright or patent law to make text and data-mining as basis for machine learning (for commercial and non-commercial purposes) easier. The rights of users and producers should be taken into account in a fair process.

To work out ethical standards regarding AI&R, the German government will work together with national and international bodies, e.g., with the German Data Ethics Commission and the EU High level expert group on AI.⁴⁹ This is stressed in its strategy document - national and international networking is very important for Germany. Development of joint guidelines with other leading regions and economic areas is a central goal.⁵⁰

References

Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany in the revised version published in the Federal Law Gazette Part III, classification number 100-1, as last amended by Article 1 of the Act of 23 December 2014 (Federal Law Gazette I p. 2438). https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_gg/englisch_gg.html

Beck S., Brauchen wir ein Roboterrecht? Ausgewählte juristische Fragen zum Zusammenleben von Menschen und Robotern (english translation: Do we need laws for robots?), 2012. <https://www.jdzb.de/fileadmin/Redaktion/PDF/veroeffentlichungen/tagungsbaende/D62/11%20p1338%20beck.pdf>

Beck S., “Grundlegende Fragen zum rechtlichen Umgang mit der Robotik” (english translation: Basic questions about the legal handling of robotics), *Juristische Rundschau*, 2009, pp. 225-230.

BGH, Urteil vom 13. Juni 2006 - VI ZR 323/04 - OLG Frankfurt a.M. 2006.

Bundesdatenschutzgesetz vom 30. Juni 2017 (BGBl. I S. 2097). English translation: https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_bdsbg/

Charisius H., “Roboter brauchen Rechte und Pflichten”, *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, 2017, <https://www.sueddeutsche.de/wissen/kuenstliche-intelligenz-roboter-brauchen-rechte-und-pflichten-1.3330222>

Daten Ethik Kommission, Recommendations of the Data Ethics Commission for the Federal Government’s Strategy on Artificial Intelligence, 2018. https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/EN/themen/it-digital-policy/recommendations-data-ethics-commission.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3

Daten Ethik Kommission, The Federal Government’s key questions to the Data Ethics Commission, 2018. https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/EN/themen/it-digital-policy/key-questions-Data-Ethics-commission.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4

Denga M., “Deliktische Haftung für künstliche Intelligenz” (english translation: Delictional liability for artificial intelligence), *Computer und Recht*, 2018, pp. 69-78.

⁴⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/high-level-expert-group-artificial-intelligence>

⁵⁰ BMWI 2018, p.8.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

German Bundestag, Gesetzentwurf der Bundesregierung, Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Änderung des Straßenverkehrsgesetzes, (Draft for a change of the road traffic act) 2017.
<http://dip21.bundestag.de/dip21/btd/18/113/1811300.pdf>

German Bundestag, Office of Technology assessment at the German Bundestag, Robotics in the care sector - challenges for society, 2017. <http://www.tab-beim-bundestag.de/en/pdf/publications/tab-fokus/TAB-Fokus-017.pdf>

German federal government, Draft Keypoints for Artificial Intelligence (Eckpunkte der Bundesregierung für eine Strategie Künstliche Intelligenz), 2018.
https://www.bmbf.de/files/180718%20Eckpunkte_KI-Strategie%20final%20Layout.pdf

German federal government, Strategie Künstliche Intelligenz der Bundesregierung (Strategy for AI) 2018. <https://www.ki-strategie-deutschland.de/home.html>

Günther J., M. Böglmüller, “Künstliche Intelligenz und Roboter in der Arbeitswelt” (english translation: Artificial intelligence and robots in the workplace), Betriebs-Berater, 2017, pp. 53-58.

Hamsch, J., D. Gorr, “In den sicheren Armen des Roboters” (english translation: In the safe arms of the robot), Versicherungs Wirtschaft 3, 2017, pp. 66-67.

Hennes D., Schwalbe, U., “Kartellbildung durch lernende Algorithmen?” (english translation: Cartel formation through learning algorithms?), *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung*, 2018.

Hilgendorf E., Automatisiertes Fahren und Strafrecht - der "Aschaffener Fall" (selfdriving cars), in: *Deutsche Richterzeitung*, 2018, pp. 66-69.

Marsiske HA, Rechte für Roboter?, *Heise*, 2016. <https://www.heise.de/newsticker/meldung/Rechte-fuer-Roboter-3334639.html>

Mitterer, K., Wiedemann, M., Zwissler, T., “BB-Gesetzgebungs- und Rechtsprechungsreport zu Industrie 4.0 und Digitalisierung 2017” (english translation: BB Legislative and Judicial Report on Industry 4.0 and Digitization 2017), *Betriebs-Berater* 2018, pp. 3-15.

Product Liability Act of 15 December 1989 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 2198), last amended by Article 180 of the regulation of 31 August 2015 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 1474). https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_prodhaftg/englisch_prodhaftg.html

SATORI, “Ethics assessments in different countries. Germany”, 2015.
<http://satoriproject.eu/media/4.e-Country-report-Germany.pdf>

Schuh J., “Willensfreiheit, Roboter und Auswahlaxiom” (english translation: Freedom of choice, robots and axiom of choice), in: Beck S. (eds.), *Jenseits von Mensch und Maschine: ethische und rechtliche Fragen zum Umgang mit Robotern, Künstlicher Intelligenz und Cyborgs*, 2012, pp. 43-75.

Simmler M., Markwalder N., “Roboter in der Verantwortung?” (english translation: robots and responsibility), *Zeitschrift für die gesamte Strafrechtswissenschaft*, 2017, p. 20.

Spindler G., “Roboter, Automation, künstliche Intelligenz, selbst-steuernde Kfz – Braucht das Recht neue Haftungskategorien?” (english translation: Robots, automation, artificial intelligence, self-driving vehicles - Does the law need new liability categories?), *Computer und Recht*, 31(12), 2015, pp. 766-776.

Teubner G., *Digital Personhood? The Status of Autonomous Software Agents in Private Law*, 2018.
<https://www.jura.uni-frankfurt.de/71719886/Digital-PersonhoodENGancilla2018.pdf>

The Act on Medical Devices of 2nd August 1994 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 1963), in the version of 7th August 2002 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 3146), last amended by Article 12 of the Act of 24th July 2010 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 983)

The German Federal Association of Corporate Lawyers (BUJ) and commercial law firm CMS: study on “Digital Economy and the Law”. <http://www.digitalisierungsstudie.com/index.php/de/startseite-digitalisierungsstudie-buj-cms-hasche-sigle>

VDMA, *Safety in Human-Robot Collaboration*, 2016.
https://robotik.vdma.org/documents/105999/16922915/1493970057035_VDMA_Position%20Paper_MRK_Safety_EN.pdf/edfe5e2d-9686-433b-93b6-30e835471546

Verordnung zur Regelung des Betriebs von unbemannten Fluggeräten. 30. März 2017, in: Bundesgesetzblatt Jahrgang 2017 Teil I Nr. 17, ausgegeben zu Bonn am 6. April 2017, pp. 683-688.
https://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/DE/Anlage/LF/verordnung-zur-regelung-des-betriebs-von-unbemannten-fluggeraeten.pdf?__blob=publicationFile

Wolfers B., “Selbstfahrende Autos: Ist das erlaubt?”, *Recht, Automobil, Wirtschaft*, 2017.
https://www.freshfields.com/globalassets/our-thinking/campaigns/digital/iot/cars/pdf/beitrag_wolfers_raw_01_17.pdf